

ADOLESCENT CONFLICTS AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: The article describes the conflicts in adolescence, mental changes, issues that deeply excite teenagers and information about the concepts of conflict and conflict situation, the psychological characteristics of adolescence, the causes of conflicts, as well as suggestions on ways to prevent conflicts.

Key words: Adolescence, mental crisis, mental changes, conflicts in adolescence.

When people hear the word conflict, they often associate it with aggression, threat, conflict, animosity, and other similar negative perceptions, resulting in the idea that conflict is always an unwanted state. But in many cases, conflicts can help identify different perspectives, provide more information, help identify more alternatives or problems. The main content of adolescence is its transition from childhood to adulthood. All aspects of development undergo qualitative restructuring, new psychological formations arise and are formed. This process of transformation determines all the main features of the personality of adolescent children, and therefore the specifics of working with them. Conflict competence is one of the leading characteristics of a person, almost any person has some conflict competence. Being an integral part of the general communicative competence, it represents the level of development of awareness of the range of possible strategies for behavior in the conflict and the ability to adequately implement these strategies in a specific life situation. In other words, conflict competence is the ability to hold a contradiction in a productive conflict form that helps to resolve it. The various conflicts during this period do not prevent biological puberty from showing its effect according to Freud, these changes. For example, which is heavy, deeply disturbing and leads to a serious mental crisis in the minds of teenagers; It can be said that

sexual maturity, which brings feelings of dissatisfaction, rudeness, stubbornness, tendency to self-analysis, subjective world and similar feelings characteristic of teenagers. A number of changes occur in the nervous system of adolescents. In this case, the activity of the subcortical part is not controlled. This is a sign of the teenager's carelessness, pettiness and emotional feelings. The character of the braking reaction is not constant. Arousal processes are sometimes so strong that the teenager is unable to control his unpleasant behavior and is unable to fully understand himself, and in this case causes conflicts for various trivial reasons. He himself is the source of most of the conflicts that arise in the process of relationships between teenagers and the people around them. This situation will be as follows. In the course of his personal relationships with people important to him, he often complains that conflicts arise between them, but he himself does not know why this happens and how to get rid of such conflicts. In this situation, it is considered to convince the teenager that he is the cause of conflicts between people. It will not be easy to do this, because teenagers who cause conflicts with people around them often strongly resist being told that they are to blame for the conflicts. Their resistance to receiving it is usually reinforced by psychological defense reactions. Psychological defense mechanisms increase because the teenager recognizes that he is the main culprit of interpersonal conflicts, lowers his self-esteem and self-esteem in the eyes of the people around him. At such a time, openly telling the teenager's fault is usually not helpful, but will only increase his defensive reaction. At such a time, he should act skillfully within the bounds of etiquette. For example, it is described that a teenager talks about interpersonal conflicts more fully, and describes the reasons and sources of their origin. If, after listening to the teenager's words, it is found that he gives bad evaluations to the other participants in the conflict and directly blames them for having caused the conflict, then the teenager himself may be to blame for the origin of the conflict. In addition, if a teenager talks about interpersonal conflicts and does not say anything about himself, his role, or only says positive thoughts about himself, then this is one of the signs that the teenager himself is to blame for

the origin of conflicts. It is not recommended to speak against the teenager even when he is justifying himself and condemning and slandering other participants in the conflict. At the same time, it is not necessary to consider everything said by a teenager as correct. The main task is to listen carefully to the teenager and instill confidence in him. At the next stage of working with a teenager, it is necessary to assume responsibility for the occurrence of interpersonal conflicts, ask the teenager to tell what needs to be changed and improved in people's behavior. This helps the teenager to understand his shortcomings in relationships with people. After that, people other than the teenager should be invited to think about what they should do to overcome their existing shortcomings and what the teenager should do against this if their partners in the relationship try to cause conflict again. In this case, the teenager does not recognize himself as the culprit of the conflict, but talks about what he can do to prevent it, that is, what he should do so that the other person does not create a conflict situation in his presence. It is better to teach concrete ways to prevent conflicts. In order for the result of the work of the school psychologist or social educator with adolescents prone to conflicts to be successful, it is necessary to develop conflict competence in the main areas: -conduct consultation work with parents and teachers aimed at removing the provoking factors of conflict behavior in adolescents; - in order for a teenager to learn how to constructively resolve their conflict situations, it is necessary to develop conflicting competence in him, that is, the ability to hold a contradiction in a productive conflict form that contributes to its resolution. Forming conflict competence, he must take into account the age and individual characteristics of the adolescent.

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